

'How did poetry get so serious? Chaucer, Langland, and the 'speculative turn' of Middle English Literature.'

Thank you very much for the invitation: this is a really welcome opportunity for me to step back from the nitty-gritty of the research I have been doing recently to reflect on the larger significance of my own, very personal interests. In particular, I would like to take some time to think about some quite 'big' questions in English, and European, literary history - and the still larger question of what we actually might mean by 'medieval literature' or even 'literature' *tout court*... I also hope that this will allow me to speak to an audience that (I assume) will be quite diverse and heterogeneous, including specialists who focus on different domains, periods, and linguistic areas...

So just to situate... a lot of my work recently has focused on the relations between literature and philosophy, and on the emergence of 'philosophical poetry' in England, but also within in a wider European context that England is very much part of (or was in the Middle Ages...). It has recently become a bit of a commonplace for me to observe that, strictly speaking, there is no such thing as 'medieval literature'. I am being slightly polemical of course, and maybe even perverse - especially in the present context where our shared and declared objective is to contribute to think about 'medieval literary studies'. But what I mean is that the notion of 'medieval literature' is an artificial and anachronistic construct. The notion of *littérature* quite simply did not exist during the medieval period: the term as we now understand it is a much later coinage, and is, I think, inevitably associated with distinctly **modern** aesthetic categories and expectations, which crystallise most firmly during the 'romantic' period.... The notion of 'literature' - and lyrical poetry in particular - implies a set of values that are, I would suggest, rather foreign to the medieval cultural dynamics that produce what I would urge us to call, quite simply 'poetry' - a category that has the double advantage of being a) more descriptive, and b) less anachronistic. Although the term 'poetry' is a notion that is no less complex and problematic than 'literature', this is a term that medieval readers and writers certainly **did** use, albeit with quite divergent ideas of how such 'poetry' ought to be, or could be, defined. (something we can return to during questions if you wish)

... but back my own immediate purpose. I'm particularly interested in trying to understand what really happens in late fourteenth-century English poetry - by which I mean poetry written not just in England, but in 'English'... What changes can we detect in poetic practice, and in the poetic theory that (often implicitly...) underpins such practice? In short: how does the 'idea' of poetry change?

I'm not telling you anything new in insisting that between about 1360 and 1400 something really profound happens in the history of English poetry. This is the generation that gives us the work of Chaucer, Langland, Gower, and the Gawain-

Poet (the 'big four', perhaps.. who used to be referred to as the 'Ricardian Poets' after John Burrow's 1973 study...), and it is also the generation that in many ways sets the course for the development of English poetry during the following century, well into the Tudor period, including the poetry of Lydgate and Hoccleve as well as that of many other less widely studied English poets, imitators, and translators. To anyone familiar with the history of English poetry, this is quite simply a well-known 'fact', and this 'fact' has constituted the basis of the kind of English literary history that has been taught in English departments for the last 80 years, and therefore has durably shaped the structure of the 'canon' of Middle English studies. It must also be said that several 'revisionist' or 'antagonistic' accounts have been offered: much excellent work has been done over the last 30 years to re-examine (and re-evaluate) what is generally referred to as 'popular Middle English literature', and particularly those English romances that are often felt to fall short of the aesthetic complexity and poetic value of the more 'canonical authors' ('lowbrow' literature.. interesting precisely because it does not appear to be very 'literary' at all, but is extremely revealing from a more strictly cultural historical perspective...); there is also a parallel tradition of alliterative poetry that (re-)emerges during the latter half of the fourteenth century (this includes of course Langland and the Gawain poet.... two of the 'big four'); and there is, arguably, the vast corpus of devotional, pastoral, and didactic literature that coexists (and in many instances intersects...) with the work of the more 'canonical' poets, particularly in the case of Gower and Lydgate, and perhaps Langland (although Langland never 'fits in' with what anyone else does...).

So there are alternative and complementary accounts that can be given... but my sense is that the basic paradigm has in fact remained unchanged, and that we continue - rightly, I believe - to assume that something really 'new' and exceptional happened in the history of English poetry between 1360 and 1400, as shaped by the 'big four' and as carried on by their fifteenth-century successors and imitators.

So my questions really is: WHAT happened in those years?

This really has to be sub-divided into two further questions:

- 1) How do we accurately describe **what** actually happened?
- 2) **How** did this transformation come about? What are its **causes**?

The first question is the trickier one - also because it will co-determine our approach to the second question. The 'traditional' answer has been, until quite recently, one that is (in my opinion) overly determined by a certain kind of literary history that works 'retrospectively', looking to our 'old', 'canonical' medieval poets in order to find evidence for those qualities that are in reality the aesthetic markers we associate with 'modern' poetry: naturalism, irony, anti-systematic thinking, secularism (possibly anti-clericalism..), metrically and imagistically pleasing constructs that challenge any ostensibly simplistic moralising platitudes. This is why in English departments we read Langland and not, say, the *Prick of Conscience*

(130 MS), or any comparable didactic work... The consensus appears to have been - for a very long time - that there simply occurs a 'quantum leap' in the quality of the kind of poetry that was produced in England - and in English - in those years. Also, there is a lingering sense that this is in large measure down to the unrivalled 'genius' of some truly spectacular 'lone individuals' that happen to have been writing in this period - even if of course many accounts of the broader 'cultural context' for this shift have been proposed, most famously perhaps the notion that there might be something like a 'Ricardian Poetry in England, as proposed by J.A. Burrow, and which suggests the existence of at least SOME shared characteristic that links all of the 'big four'. But such arguments about the broader 'context' belong to the second question (the question of what CAUSED this shift...) and I want to put that to one side for the moment..., to stick with the first question of 'how we should actually describe' this shift.

So, as I said, the distinctive difference of this kind of new poetry has often been felt to be of an aesthetic nature: this is, quite simply, a kind of poetry that shares some of the formal and aesthetic features that we - in English departments and in literature departments more generally - tend to value: it is poetry that is artful, subtle, carefully patterned, perhaps elegantly hesitant and undecided... and thus deserves to be taught alongside the variously 'modern' poetry of Milton, Wordsworth, Elizabeth Bishop, or indeed Baudelaire... and not alongside the excessively schematic, and aesthetically 'backward' didactic poetry of the *Prick of Conscience* or similar works...

And this is precisely the reason for my own 'beef' with the whole idea of 'literature'!... Yes, there is no denying that this late fourteenth-century poetry is aesthetically complex and perhaps even 'pleasing'.... But my point is rather that the **reasons** for that change are not primarily of an aesthetic order. In fact, I would say that the aesthetic shift is a secondary effect of a very different process, which is determined by a changing understanding of the **purpose, ambition, nature, and intrinsic power** of poetic writing itself.

A simple - and perhaps slightly crude way of putting this - is contained in my title for today: poetry, quite simply, gets extremely 'serious': suddenly it is 'highbrow' stuff; intellectually challenging. We could call this a 'philosophical turn', but I prefer the term 'speculative': it describes poetry that is intellectually ambitious, even though it perhaps lacks the 'systematic' character we associate with a philosophical project in the strict sense. Critics often speak of an 'aesthetics of irresolution' in relation to this poetry: my point is that such an aesthetics is simply the collateral, secondary effect of a project that is primarily intellectual - i.e. it is interested in exploring the possible uses of poetic language as a tool for intellectual speculation.

This 'speculative turn' produces poetry that is intellectually more challenging than anything that precedes (or perhaps it is challenging in a different way...), and this in turn has the collateral effect also is that its imaginative constructions (the metrical, thematic, and imagistic configurations...or in short the rhetorical CRAFT...) also becomes more complex articulated, textured, nuanced, and dynamic, since it needs to support a far more ambitious poetic project than any poets previously writing in English, say before 1360, would have dared to propose...

When you come to think of it, this actually makes a lot of sense: I (for one) struggle to think of any Middle English poetry that is characterised by the kind of intellectual ambition that could be meaningfully compared with the poetry produced by the 'big four'. Please do let me know if you can think of something - I would really like and need to know!

Just take as a term of comparison a poem like the *Owl and the Nightingale*... This is a debate poem that is clearly informed by 'intellectual' or more accurately 'clerical' traditions in some sense: its tone fluctuates between the abusive and mundane on the one hand, and the scholastic and intellectual on the other, and of course the poem ends by appealing to the offices of the mysterious Nicholas of Guildford.. only he could resolve this mock-epic quarrel between birds. The poem is clearly informed by schoolroom practice and intellectual traditions more widely - but its purview is far more modest, bordering on the occasional and anecdotal. The tone is - furthermore - far less 'serious', and less 'philosophical' than anything found in later literature - even in Chaucer's most famous beast fable, the Nun's priest tale, where barnyard humour rubs shoulders with references to some allusions frankly rather challenging philosophical problems: the tone of the allusions may be light-hearted, but there is no doubting the seriousness of the philosophical frames of reference that are playfully invoked (and then abandoned...): the nature of fate and predestination; the contingency of the future; the status of the imagination - all problems that are very much at the forefront of contemporary debates in the Universities...

It is not a surprise, then, that readers (both medieval and modern), should come to think of the 'Ricardian poets' as 'philosophical' in one way or another... **CITE** Chaucer was referred to as a philosopher by his own contemporaries: Thomas Usk (another speculative writer...) calls him 'oure noble philosophical poete in English; in 1387; Eustache Deschamps (1385-93) calls him 'Socrates plain de philosophie'; for Thomas Hoccleve (in 1411) he is '**heir in philosophie / to Aristotle in our tonge**'. **CITE** Langland has been referred to by the editors of the 2014 Cambridge *Companion to Piers Plowman* "a poet who is more perceptive than any other contemporary philosopher on what constitutes the grounds of philosophy and thought, questioning those very bases" , 'Christian Philosophy in *Piers Plowman*', p. 142

As I've already flagged, 'philosophical poetry' is perhaps a bit overstated or overdetermined - my personal preference would be to say that this poetry is 'intellectually ambitious', and that it pursues (and promotes) intellectual speculation in its readers.

What I mean by 'intellectually ambitious' and speculative probably needs some clarifying: I do not necessarily mean 'learned' - although more often than not intellectual speculation does presuppose some degree of learning. Indeed, this is a really central question in Langland's *Piers Plowman*: how much learning - and of what kind exactly - is necessary to ensure the salvation of one's soul, or indeed the reformation of secular and/or ecclesiastical institutions? And how is one supposed to use that learning? **CITE** (*Study on the difficulty of understanding the theology of the Trinity*)

'Alle þe clerkes vnder Crist ne koude þis assoille,
But þus it bilongeþ to bileue to lewed þat willen dowel.
For hadde neuere freke fyn wit þe feiþ to dispute,
Ne man hadde no merite, myȝt it ben ypreued;
(B XI.247-50)

Langland's point, as I understand it - and the point I want to make more broadly **about** Langland's poetry as well as that of Chaucer, Gower, and the Gawain-Poet - is that learning in itself is not enough, and can actually be detrimental, providing a false sense of security and intellectual arrogance that is ultimately deleterious.

The Canterbury Tales are full of instances of the misuse of technical, and more specifically 'scholastic' learning of various kinds: we have the more 'innocent' and good-humoured examples of Nicholas in the Miller's Tale, or Aleyn and John in the Reeve's Tale (who are all students, one in Oxford and the two others in Cambridge). Here 'highbrow' learning is simply used to gain a social and sexual advantage - in the case of the Miller's tale this focuses on natural science, and more specifically astronomy + divination, the preserve of students in the Arts Faculty **CITE**; and in the Reeve's Tale the learning in question is of legal nature - as indeed would have been the case for student at 'Soler Hall', where Chaucer places John and Aleyn, where the vast majority of students in the 1380 would have been studying law... **CITE** But we have the more sinister and threatening examples for the misuse of clerical learning: the Friar, the Summoner, and the Pardoner, whose pursuit of personal interest entails the dismantling of the social, moral, and sacramental practices of the late medieval Church. Or - to put it bluntly - whose collateral effect is simply the mass perdition of the faithful and (if we want to be VERY serious and somewhat melodramatic...), the corruption of the apostolic role of the Church and the advent of Antichrist. Now the unleashing of Antichrist is of course the central theme of the closing passus of *Piers Plowman*... and here too this possibility is closely linked to the misuse of clerical learning - more specifically the

teaching about the central role of Contrition in the Sacrament of Penance. This is precisely what is undermined by 'Sir Penetrans domos', aka 'friar flatterer'

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And Langland ALWAYS, invariably associates Friars very specifically with University learning - and particularly with the discipline of logic...

: **CITE**: Langland's Envy 'heet freres go to scole / And lerne logyk and lawe, and also contemplacion' (B XX.273-4), and 'freres to philosophie he fond hem to scole' (B XX.296)

((((((((Gower - by contrast - is perhaps less starkly 'apocalyptic', but he too is engaged in writing poetry that explicitly and directly seeks to tackle the social, moral, and intellectual corruption of his age. While his approach is perhaps less insistently philosophical (because it is more overtly political), his poetry too ultimately seeks to address social ills by inviting reflection and analysis: in the Confessio proposes storytelling as a way of 'glossing', and 'thinking through' contemporary crises in ways that are enabling and transformative, and that (ideally) will inspire the reforming agenda of the Monarch.))))))

This is all perhaps a long and roundabout way of saying that what I call the 'speculative turn' of late fourteenth Century English poetry should by no means be equated with some sort of unproblematic celebration of the power of clerical and/or scholastic learning: this is not simply *vulgarisation des savoirs*... (vernacularisation). On the contrary, I would suggest that such poetry is 'speculative' precisely because it is willing, and able, to contemplate open-ended questions - including the problem of the 'value of learning' itself (!). The poetry is speculative because it asks often difficult, sometimes troubling questions that do not appear to have a clear answer... "Irresolution" it certainly is... but it is not an "**aesthetics** of irresolution": if anything it is an affirmation of 'irresolution as an ethical imperative' (!).

So, I think I've essentially given you my own (tentative, provisional, incomplete..) answer to the first question of **WHAT** actually happens in late fourteenth-century poetry. And I'd be keen to hear of any challenges or counter-arguments... because I have not really formulated this hypothesis in these precise terms until quite recently..

So **how** did this transformation come about? What are its **causes**?

It is certainly fair to say that there are multiple factors and multiple contexts that need to be taken into account here - and it is worth acknowledging that we will probably never be able to have something like a 'complete picture' or an

'exhaustive' explanation of how this change came about. So I will try to concentrate on a couple factors that seem to me particularly important - the answer is again tentative and provisional...

It is certainly tempting - of course - to put the causes down to a mixture of **intellectual** and **sociological** factors - which it is difficult to separate and which have to be discussed together.

It is often argued that the late fourteenth century was a period where previously specialised learning did become more widely accessible - and that certainly is the case! For example, we do witness the proliferation of translations of 'learned' materials into English, often of an encyclopaedic nature such as the translations undertaken by John Trevisa (Bart Anglicus *De Proprietatibus rerum*; R Higden's *Polychronicon*; or works in the tradition of the pseudo-Aristotelian *Secretum Secretorum*, such as *Wise Book of Philosophy and Astronomy* and other similar knock-offs in ME). But this really is pretty low-level stuff for the most part (although not irrelevant), and this really is (I would suggest) in the order of the *vulgarisation des savoirs*... The kind of 'philosophical' texture of 'Ricardian Poetry' (for want of a better word..) strikes me of being of a very different, and ultimately more 'elitist' kind... Scholars like William Courtenay and other intellectual historians have pointed to a rather different development, and namely the widening circulation of intellectuals that could count on varying levels of exposure to University learning in those very years - a development that is closely tied to the accelerating transformation in the administrative machinery of Church and state. It's important to remember that - crudely put - only very few 'intellectuals' during the fourteenth century would attend university with the aim of becoming something like 'academics', and only very few of the masters who lectured in the Universities (in the Arts Faculty in particular) would envisage staying at university. In fact, it is a slight misconception to speak of 'scholastic philosophers' or even 'theologians', because more often than not those 'philosophers' would go on to exercise various forms of clerical and administrative duties (at court, in the city of London, or in secular or ecclesiastical institutions of various kinds...). Most students in fact left University without a degree once they felt they had acquired enough skills of one kind or another to get a job - which strikes me as providing an interesting contrast with nowadays... where everyone collects diplomas like baseball cards while learning very little in the process (rant over...).

Universities allowed students to specialise in arcane subjects, for sure - but this was no ivory tower - the proof, again, can be found in the 'clerical' Tales from Chaucer's Canterbury pilgrimage, where both the Tale's narrators and all the other pilgrims (and of course Chaucer himself) all demonstrate a very nuanced and fine-grained understanding not only of the University world, but also of its interactions with the 'outside world' - and in some ways the Miller's and Reeve's, and perhaps Franklin's tales, are very much 'town vs. gown' stories.

There is some interesting circumstantial evidence. Chaucer famously dedicates his magnum opus - *Troilus & Criseyde* - to the attention of 'moral Gower' and 'philosophical Strode' **CITE**. Now even my intellectual historian colleagues generally respond by saying 'oh, is that Ralph Strode the Logician' - but that is already a misnomer... There isn't such a thing as a professional 'logician' in this period, but only, at best, someone with an expertise in logic that could be bothered to produce a treatise or a series of *questiones* in logic at some point in their lives - which is exactly what Strode did, writing a six-part manual on Logic, comprising an introductory *Summula*; *De principiis logicalibus*; *Suppositiones*, *Consequentie*, *Obligationes*, and *Insolubilia*. But by the time Chaucer addresses Strode, he is a logician no more, and in fact works as a *Common Pleader* for the City of London - a post he held from 1374 until 1387, and in which capacity Chaucer knew him, and almost certainly first met him. Another example of a similar bridge' between the University world and the Urban environment of London is provided by Richard Kilvington - Master in Arts and Doctor in Theology at Oxford - and author of a collection of *Sophismata*, a commentary on Aristotle's ethics, and a on P Lombard's Sentences - became Dean of the Almonry school at St Paul between 1354 and 1361 - the school that Chaucer almost certainly attended as a child, in the years immediately preceding Kilvington's arrival... Even more interesting, Kilvington served as a diplomat and ambassador for Edward III before becoming Dean of St Paul's - a very good illustration of the permeable boundaries that linked three otherwise VERY different environments that we tend to consider separately: the City, the University, and the Court...

This is therefore a world where social mobility (of a kind...) is facilitated not only by the plague - as every introduction to the *Canterbury Tales* reminds us - but where people move between places and institutions, and of course ideas and texts move with the people and through the people. Some 30 years ago Ann Astell already observed that the consequence of this was 'a clericalisation of society', and more recent work has provided some much-needed insight into the socio-intellectual dynamics of this period. Chris Cannon, for instance, in *From Literacy to Literature*, has argued that many of the 'stylistic' features, but also the underlying intellectual *habitus* that underpins much of the canonical 'Ricardian Poetry' in fact has its origin in the schoolroom, in the Grammar or Cathedral schools that provided the basic training for a wide range of 'clerks' who would go on to become administrators and sometimes (*aux heures perdues...*), poets. Cannon also has an important point to make about the specific nature of the kind of education that informs this poetry: contrary to what is often assumed, Cannon insists that the dominant intellectual influence on Ricardian poets is not that of advanced philosophical or theological speculation, but of fairly basic, solidly grammatical education. I think this is an important corrective to the rather optimistic, and to my mind often (but not

always) unconvincing arguments that Chaucer and Langland would have been *au fait* with the latest cutting-edge developments in the Arts and Theology Faculties of their day - such as the nominalist reduction of Aristotle's categories by Ockham, the revolutionary quantitative methods of the *Calculatores* of Merton College, or indeed the rarefied debates on questions such as abstractive vs. intuitive cognition according to Scotus, Walter Chatton or Adam of Wodeham... The only corrective I would formulate is that perhaps the dividing line between 'advanced' and 'elementary' education is less clear-cut than Cannon assumes... and the presence of Richard Kilvington as Dean of St Paul and thus nominal Head of the Almonry School attached to it is only one illustration of the 'permeable' nature of this boundary between 'higher' and 'elementary' education.

Another factor that enhances the circulations of philosophical and theological ideas around London - because this really is a strictly metropolitan development - is, somewhat paradoxically, the fact that the City of London had no University: this means that the City would rely on a steady supply of University-educated men (and yes, it is just men unfortunately..) who would arrive in the capital and engage in a much wider network of personal and professional relations than they would have cultivated during their University days, at Oxford or Cambridge (or perhaps Paris, but that was a declining trend...). this means that University-trained men would come and go through the *studia* of the mendicant orders in London, would deliver sermons that in one way or another capitalised on, and thus gave wider currency to, their university education. They also often become embroiled in relatively public debates of varying degrees of acrimony over theological matters - this is after all the period that leads up to the very public condemnation of Wyclif's propositions in London in 1382. Staying clear of all the trouble he later caused, for my own purpose it is interesting to observe that earlier in his life Wyclif became exchanged in a rather friendly intellectual exchange with a certain Ralph Strode - fellow alumnus of Merton College, Oxford - while in London. This is almost certain the Strode who is also a logician and Chaucer-friend, and the connection illustrates very well the fluid and expanding nature of the kinds of social networks that would crystallise among men of this undefined 'group'.

We know a bit (but still very little...) about men like Wyclif and Strode, but there are dozens of nameless figures who move in this ill-defined and fluid space in between the different worlds of the Universities, the Inns of Court, the City, and the Royal court and its administration, and ecclesiastical institutions of various kinds. Kathryn Kerby-Fulton has recently coined the wonderful phrase 'the clerical proletariat' to describe this new 'breed' of men who were not quite intellectuals and not quite administrators, and who were often essentially 'unattached', and thus free to interact with wealthy and ambitious Londoners as well as their patrons or employers, secular or ecclesiastical, and (of course, and especially..) free to interact with each other. Another representative of this nebulous group is Thomas Usk - soon-to-be headless friend of Chaucer, and fellow adapter of Boethius, and

certainly very much invested in the project of producing a new kind of intellectually ambitious poetry in English - even if the result / outcome of his efforts, the *Testament of Love*, cannot be considered an unequivocal success story...

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So, to conclude this short 'sociological' excursus.... my main point is that there definitely are circumstantial, socio-intellectual reasons for the emergence of this 'New' kind of intellectual poetry in London and perhaps beyond (the Gawain-poet, at least, is NOT a London poet). My final point, however, is that these reasons are enough to create 'the circumstances' for the emergence of this new kind of poetry, but they are not its primary 'causes' or even 'triggers'. The primary cause for this 'speculative turn' in English poetry - in my opinion - is to be sought across the channel, in France, with the emergence of a poetic tradition that is just as focused on asserting its own credentials as a legitimate, or at least respectable form of intellectual speculation.

This is a tradition that for all intents and purposes begins with Jean de Meun's continuation of the *Roman de la Rose*, completed in the 1270 - although of course the influence of 'clerical' traditions and university culture is discernible in the work of earlier French/Parisian authors > Alain Corbellari, *La Voix des Clercs*....

But it is with the Rose that everything really gets going. Now we think of the RR primarily as a 'courtly' poem, and true enough it is about 'love'. But while its subject may not be 'academic' in any sense, its approach - its plural *formae tractandi*, if you will - certainly owes much to the kind of learning available within the University. Jean de Meun clearly is an author who is a product of the Universities (in one way or another...), and we have known this for over a century... but I think it is only in recent years that we have begun to appreciate exactly how his scholastic exposure inflects, or rather infuses, the project of the Roman de la Rose. The old, 'default' image of JdM was that of Gérard Paré, who in the 1940s argued that Jean de Meun 'est un vulgarisateur et un traducteur [qui] continue de mettre à la portée des laïcs les rudiments de sa science universitaire'. '[Ses] vagues dissertations scientifiques [. . .] apparaissent comme de l'enfantillage [. . .] et n'[ont] aucune prétention scientifique' Gérard Paré, *Les idées et les lettres au XIII^e siècle: Le Roman de la Rose* (Montreal: Bibliothèque de Philosophie, 1947), pp. 265, 311. C.S. Lewis was not much different: for him JdM was a 'bungler', a sort of overzealous amateur whose learning was sufficient to persuade him into pursuing an ambitious project, but dramatically insufficient to allow him to structure and organise that project meaningfully and logically...

In recent years a very different account has emerged: the apparent pitfalls, inconsistencies, sudden changes of direction/perspective, and the generally disruptive nature of the RR are not - it would seem - the result of incompetence, but they are the intrinsic means through which the poem seeks to challenge the

certainties and assumptions of its readers. Rather than reproducing scholastic learning quite inertly for 'les laïcs', the *Rose* in fact challenges and stress-tests many of the axiomatic assumptions that underlie University learning in the late XIII cent., and attempts to propose its own strategies for intellectual speculation in narrative form. And here too I think we have been somewhat blinded by our quite narrow 'literary' goggles, because yes, of course the use of the first-person dreamer-narrator-commentator persona is a major literary innovation... but (and to my mind more importantly) it also allows the articulation of a distinct kind of subjectivity. The 'philosophical project' of the *Rose*, then (if I can be forgiven for using the term...), is a strictly subjectivistic one: instead of being interested in pursuing demonstrative knowledge on the basis of syllogistic proof (following Aristotle), the *Rose* is interested in different forms of knowledge, more 'phenomenological' you could say. The poem explores 'how' we know, and offers itself up as a thought experiment for the reader', opening up a realm of possibilities for imaginative projection that the reader can inhabit through an act of interpretation **CITE**. It is as if the reader - who participates in the poem's own 'I' - is invited to step into the poem, as a way of confronting a wide range of problems, debates, situations that raise deeply philosophical questions... Poetic fiction provides the opportunity to 'inhabit' a concrete and specific situation - and thus of course fosters an eminently **active** readerly participation... The reader does, literally, become an *acteur*

I won't go into too much detail about this, also because I've written on the matter and published a book with Jonathan Morton to try and examine the problem more fully.... But I think that we have only just begun to understand how the *Rose* works, and to understand the depth and magnitude of the transformations it brings about on the scene of European, and not just French, literature and culture during the later Middle Ages. It doesn't help - paradoxically - that we are all familiar with the *Roman de la Rose* to some degree... because this is precisely why we take it for granted and tend to miss what is deeply extraordinary about it. So I think we need to put to bed this idea that the *Roman de la Rose* is simply a 'courtly' poem - or a sort of messy encyclopaedia, or merely an anti-feminist pamphlet like Christine de Pizan would have us believe, or just a big joke. It is - of course - all of these things, but the whole is more than the sum of its part. The distinctive feature of the *Rose* is that it offers itself up as a tool for active intellectual speculation for the reader - and once all is said and done, I also believe that this is the single most important reason why it proved so popular. It is a spectacularly 'open' text: it promises - but also determinedly withholds any deeper 'vérité'.

One important - but exclusively French/francophone strand of this 'deep' influence of the *rose*, and its impact on how the very idea of poetry was transformed in its wake, is examined in what I think is a really important book by S Kay and A Armstrong: *Knowing Poetry (une muse savante)*. The *Rose* here plays a major role in triggering a vogue for poetry that is not only perceived as artful, graceful, and (at best) ethical, but it introduces the idea that poetry conveys

knowledge, and that poetry might be able to crystallise forms of knowledge that *differ* - and therefore interrogate, supplement, or come into conflict with - existing forms of knowledge, particularly those codified within the highly regulated environment of the medieval University. We are very far from a simple *vulgarisation des savoirs*... and the key element is, to my mind, the desire to use poetry as a tool for active intellectual exploration - not just as a vehicle to convey forms of knowledge that already exist, and that are simply 'transposed' into verse...

Just a few words on the English reception of the *Rose* - and then perhaps a word of caution about the risks that come with placing such huge importance on a single text... It really isn't anything very new to say that the *Rose* was an important influence on English 'Ricardian' poetry... we all know that. But I think that for a long time we have mistakenly considered the *Rose* to be simply one text among many others - and probably not an overly interesting one - that 'Ricardian Poets' and later authors 'plundered' for their own reasons, borrowing this or that detail, character, episode, or turn of phrase... Again, the *rose* undeniable DOES provide such occasional 'raw materials' - but its real impact is to be sought at a much deeper level. The impact of the *Rose* is not just localised or not even 'widespread' or 'ubiquitous' - I would call it 'systemic'. It seems to me it transforms the practice of poetic writing by introducing the idea that vernacular poetry - first in French and then in English - CAN become a means for intellectual speculation. Again; I think this is less to do with 'the emergence of a new model of 'authorship' (and I personally find this focus on 'authorship, again, to be rather too 'literary' and thus quite 'unmedieval..'), than with the transformation of the very definition of what poetry IS and what it is capable of achieving. Poetry does become a dynamic tool to 'think through' a number of very serious questions that are - for want of a better word perhaps - 'philosophical'. And the questions are sophisticated, even if poetry is often not very interested in proposing 'solutions' to its own problems.... In fact, I would say that much of the 'seriousness' of this poetry comes precisely from its willingness to confront questions for which we seem to LACK the answer.... This

This idea that the *Rose* deeply 'transforms' both the idea and the practice of writing poetry (in England as well as France - and of course Italy, which I've left out of the picture today...) has been an important assumption that has underpinned a lot of my own work, and luckily now we have a monograph (not mine!) that provides what I think is precisely the kind of transformative reconsideration of the place and role of the *Rose* in the 'Making of English Literature' (Philip Knox).

I think that this book really has the potential to transform how we think about 'English' literary history - and also provides a salutary reminder of the fact that many of the things we assume to be most distinctively 'English' about 'English Literature' in this period are - in fact - French (!). My own angle on this question recently has been to examine the French influence on William Langland - a poet who writes alliterative verse, that most Anglo-Saxon of poetic forms, and who we

often think of as 'the most quint-essentially English' of all Medieval English poets. Langland's case is interesting precisely because the deep, I would say 'systemic' impact of the *Rose*, which becomes all but invisible if you focus merely on the verbal surface of the text - which of course is resolutely Anglo-Saxon. But the impact of the *Rose* is all the stronger for being nearly invisible, and develops an almost 'tectonic' character, shaping the movements and alignments of the large conceptual 'bedrock' upon which Langland's poem is built and (even more importantly) tracing the fault lines along which the poem 'moves' and shifts over time...

It's impossible for me to illustrate this for you today in such short time - you'll have to read the book... But one thing that Langland's case helps us to realise, is that the *Rose* is a text that never travels on its own, and that more often than not the poem will come with a much wider baggage of accumulated 'intertexts' and 'paratexts' that become attached to it as it travels through France, and Europe, from 1280 into 1600. In Langland's case - and indeed in the case of Chaucer and MANY other English readers - one of the texts that becomes indissolubly linked to the *Roman de la Rose* is the corpus of *Pèlerinages* Poems produced by the Cistercian Monk Guillaume de Deguileville between about 1331 and 1358: the PVH, PA, and PJC. The first of these three long allegorical poems is in fact a sort of 'response' to the *Rose*, and tellingly one manuscript colophon presents this as an 'exposé sur le roman de la Rose'.... A sort of rewriting that is also a gloss, seeking to clarify the original text while countering it with a project of its own. Crucially, the *Pèlerinages* presuppose the reader's familiarity with the *Rose*... and what we know about its reception history suggests that readers were very much aware of this connection - including in England, where the *Pèlerinages* were translated on multiple occasions in the early fifteenth century, and seem to have circulated widely.

The *Pèlerinages* - like the *Rose*, but much more so - have had a pretty terrible press in terms of their perceived 'literary value' - in fact they were all but ignored until about 15 years ago.... But here too we have a text that we have dramatically underestimated and misrepresented: far from being simply a text full of didactic and homiletic banalities, the poems propose a hugely ambitious programme for the moral, spiritual, and intellectual development of its readers.... something that was not lost on a reader like Langland. Langland truly uses the two texts as glosses on each other - reading the *Rose* through the *Pèlerinages*, and vice versa..... - and to my mind it is simply unimaginable that he would have been able to produce a poem like *Piers Plowman* - with its multiple dream visions and its multiple versions - without having 'absorbed' and pondered at length the poems of his two French predecessors.

To conclude, then: the *Pèlerinages* are a particularly strong and sustained example for what a response to the *Rose* could look like, and how those responses gradually create a wider 'field' of texts that are best seen as participating in the original

project of the Rose - namely, the belief in the idea that poetry had a distinctive speculative purpose thanks to its inherent and distinctive cognitive potential. Countless other texts enter this field, and create an ever-expanding corpus of vernacular poetry - often of a broadly 'allegorical character' - that sees itself no longer as simply producing 'beautiful lies', but as facilitating access to some form of deeper 'truth'. Once this originally French 'turn' becomes established in England, it is here to stay - and it carries on shaping the mainstream of English literary production well into the Tudor period.

Ultimately then, it appears to be the fault of the French - and not of William of Ockham, Ralph Strode, John Dumbleton and their Oxford pals - if English poetry started taking itself so seriously at the end of the XIV century.

missed the most important and

>> **Stephen Hawes** is a striking late example of what this development means: he incessantly invokes Chaucer, Gower, and Lydgate; yet his poetry is nothing like that of his predecessors (in fact one does wonder if he ever read Chaucer with much attention..). But the one area in which his poetry most clearly latches on to the poetry of his 'heroes' and predecessors, is the conviction that the poetry harbours some deeper form of 'truth', and that this truth needs to be recovered through a careful, painstaking readerly engagement with the text. In one word, this could be defined as the 'allegorical' character of poetry - the idea that the literal surface (or 'husk') of the narrative conceals some deeper, truer, and more valuable meaning that is accessible to readers who are adequately equipped to 'hear' or 'decipher' that deeper meaning.

And - crucially - Hawes shares the 'French fetish' of much of this 'English poetry'...

'larger significance' of my own, very personal interests, in terms of English literary history and, in fact, European literary history.